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BEENET: MONITORING BEES AND BIODIVERSITY
ACROSS MEDITERRANEAN AGRO-ENVIRONMENTS

*BeeNet: monitoraggio delle api e della biodiversità
negli agro-ecosistemi del Mediterraneo*

Wild bees became more and more popular lately. Along with other wild pollinators, they are the subject and the tool at ones. In Mediterranean areas, there are numerous studies focusing on bees, hoverflies and Lepidoptera. In some cases, pollinators are the main subject of the monitoring (examples in BARTUAL *et al.*, 2018; ROPARS *et al.*, 2020), while in other studies pollinators and other arthropods are a tool to understand the reproduction of given plant species (examples in GALLONI *et al.*, 2008; GIOVANETTI *et al.*, 2020).

Concerning wild bees, the Mediterranean area is a biodiversity hotspot: in Italy the list includes 944 species (PAGLIANO, 1995), 48.05% of all European species (NIETO *et al.*, 2014). Wild bees are addressed for concerns on bee decline, but they are also expected to indicate and measure how much the environment is affected by human impacts (GALLAI *et al.*, 2009). Numerous studies confirm the importance, for agriculture, of adjacent non-cultivated areas as field margins or forest patches (MORRISON *et al.*, 2017). In the Mediterranean, yearly flowering fluctuations are frequent (FLO *et al.*, 2018), and may result in significant yearly changes in flower composition. The application of landscape ecology to studies dealing with pollinators is relatively new, but it rapidly increased in its predictive power. Investigating wild bees, therefore, can not be disentangled from concurrently considering the influ-

ence of landscape and plants on bee nesting and foraging activities (GIOVANETTI *et al.*, 2021).

However, basic information on species distribution and abundance are often lacking (NIETO *et al.*, 2014). BeeNet (2019-2023) is a national monitoring project that provides data on wild bees, and the plants they visit in Italian agro-ecosystems. The aims include improving regional wild bee species lists, defining shared and exclusive plant-pollinator networks of agricultural landscapes, contributing to the assessment of efficacy of CAP (Common Agricultural Policy) measures. The project is built on the base of a network including the main frameworks: environment, food sources, bee identification. To start with, we defined the sampling sites based on soil use descriptors widely adopted, the Corine Land Cover (CLC) inventory (BÜTTNER *et al.*, 2004). We focus on agro-environments, both for their impact on the national territory and the importance for the socio-economic perspective. Since agricultural practices may vary, we choose to place our sampling sites at the two extremes of the agro-environment: intensively cultivated and semi-natural, where agriculture is carried out in proximity of protected areas. This decision allows to verify congruity of descriptors in regions with very different agro-environmental characteristics, as we may find in a diverse country as Italy.

In 11 Italian regions, the project surveys monthly two sampling sites, except for two regions where three sites have been selected for continuity with previous monitoring plans: therefore, we can count on 24 sites. For all site, on-site validation was carried out to select similar and adequate conditions to ensure a long-term monitoring along the three years of the project. At each site, we carry out a monthly monitoring of a fixed transect of 200 x 2m, catching with an insect net all wild bee individuals foraging in it. Records refer to captured specimens and plant species in bloom: specimens are sent to the entomological laboratory for the identification at species level, plants are identified in loco through Pl@ntNet app (BONNET *et al.*, 2020) or collected when identification is doubtful. Data are then combined and analyzed to identify common trends and peculiar situations: preliminary results are already available.

BeeNet build a strong network that for the first time concentrate a country-wide amount of data (field monitoring), samples (bee and plant specimens) and expertise (the project coordination and team at CREA-AA, and collaborators from Italian universities). This project will therefore certainly step up the state-of-the art of wild bees in Italy, contributing at once to a better knowledge on Mediterranean species and their

distribution in agro-environments. It will also provide the basic information on wild bees' abundance and distribution to define a tool to be implemented in the validation of agricultural practice and their implementation through the next CAP policies.

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